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Abstract: This study aims to explore shape variability of the acetabulum during the human adult life span, in relation to sex and age. The human acetabular shape was analysed in 682 os coxae from three different documented skeletal collections from the Iberian Peninsula. Two landmarks and thirty-two sliding semi-landmarks were used for the geometric morphometric procedures and a clock-wise standard was used for orientation. The 180° meridian (6:00) line was positioned over the midpoint of the acetabular notch and 36 reference points in 10° increments along the rim were marked. Data showed that size, sex and age significantly influence acetabular shape variation. Sex differences were significant in individuals younger than 65 years old and were characterised by males exhibiting relatively extended acetabular rim profiles from 10:00 to 1:00, narrower acetabular notches, and reduced acetabular fossae. In addition, three main age-related changes occurred to the acetabular shape in both sexes: outer acetabular profile modification, with extension from 10:00 to 1:00 and reduction from 7:00 to 9:00, acetabular notch narrowing, and acetabular fossa reduction. The age-related changes that were observed are shared by both sexes and seem to be related to bone production associated with age. Specifically, age appears to affect the entire border of the lunate surface: the acetabular rim, both acetabular horns, and the outer edge of the acetabular fossa. Furthermore, shape data confirmed the clover-leaf shape of the acetabular fossa in both males and females. These results improve our understanding of acetabular shape, and assist in refining age-estimation methods and enhancing hip surgery and rehabilitation.

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Shape variability of the adult human acetabulum and acetabular fossa related to sex and age by geometric morphometrics. Implications for adult age estimation

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HIGHLIGHTS

- 682 acetabula were analysed by geometric morphometrics taken into account sex and age.
- Acetabular shape variation depends on factors as size, sex and age.
- Acetabular fossa has a clover-leaf morphology.
- Males have wider lunate surfaces, narrower notches and smaller fossae than females.
- With age acetabular fossa lose its clover-leaf shape, becoming more rounded.

SHAPE VARIABILITY OF THE ADULT HUMAN ACETABULUM AND ACETABULAR FOSSA RELATED TO SEX AND AGE BY GEOMETRIC MORPHOMETRICS. IMPLICATIONS FOR ADULT AGE ESTIMATION

ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore shape variability of the acetabulum during the human adult life span, in relation to sex and age. The human acetabular shape was analysed in 682 os coxae from three different documented skeletal collections from the Iberian Peninsula. Two landmarks and thirty-two sliding semi-landmarks were used for the geometric morphometric procedures and a clock-wise standard was used for orientation. The 180° meridian (6:00) line was positioned over the midpoint of the acetabular notch and 36 reference points in 10° increments along the rim were marked. Data showed that size, sex and age significantly influence acetabular shape variation. Sex differences were significant in individuals younger than 65 years old and were characterised by males exhibiting relatively extended acetabular rim profiles from 10:00 to 1:00, narrower acetabular notches, and reduced acetabular fossae. In addition, three main age-related changes occurred to the acetabular shape in both sexes: outer acetabular profile modification, with extension from 10:00 to 1:00 and reduction from 7:00 to 9:00, acetabular notch narrowing, and acetabular fossa reduction. The age-related changes that were observed are shared by both sexes and seem to be related to bone production associated with age. Specifically, age appears to affect the entire border of the lunate surface: the acetabular rim, both acetabular horns, and the outer edge of the acetabular fossa. Furthermore, shape data confirmed the clover-leaf shape of the acetabular fossa in both males and females. These results improve our understanding of acetabular shape, and assist in refining age-estimation methods and enhancing hip surgery and rehabilitation.

KEYWORDS: Hip joint; Adult age estimation; Ageing, Osteoarthritis; Acetabular shape; Morphology; Anatomy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The acetabulum, a part of its locomotor implication, is important because of its utility in sex estimation (e.g., Genovés, 1959; Rissech & Malgosa, 1997; Murphy, 2000; Albanese, 2003; Benazzi et al. 2008; Macaluso, 2011), and because recently it has been identified as a good adult age marker (Rougé-Maillart et al. 2004; Rissech et al. 2006, 2007; Rougé-Maillart et al. 2007, 2009; Calce & Rogers, 2011; Calce, 2012; Mays, 2012, 2014; San-Millán et al. 2016). The original acetabular method (Rissech et al. 2006) for estimating adult age-at-death studied exclusively acetabular age changes in males (Rissech et al. 2006; 2007). Some authors reported no sex differences in their obtained age estimations when Rissech's method was applied in both males and females (Rougé-Maillart et al. 2007; Stull & James, 2010; Calce, 2012). However, in these studies there was not any specific analysis on sex differences. Recently some authors have indicated the existence of possible sex differences in acetabular ageing rate between males and females (Mays, 2012; San-Millán, 2015; San-Millán et al. 2016). Specifically, females seem to show a slower rate of ageing than males in this anatomical area. These discordances between authors highlight the necessity of having a better and more detailed knowledge of this anatomical element, taking into account age and sex.

The metric variation of the acetabulum in relation to sex and its functional anatomy have been extensively studied for anthropological (Genovés, 1959; Rissech & Malgosa, 1997; Murphy, 2000; Albanese, 2003; Benazzi et al. 2008; Macaluso, 2011), medical and biomechanical (Noguchi et al. 1999; Thompson et al. 2000; Gupta et al. 2001; Antoniadis et al. 2001; Tallroth & Lepistö, 2006; Ganz et al. 2008; Vandenbussche et al. 2008; Köhnlein et al. 2009; Krebs et al. 2009; Nakahara et al. 2011; Bonneau et al. 2012; Zeng et al. 2012, among others) purposes. However, the acetabular and fossa morphology have rarely been analysed in detail and much less from an anthropological point of view (Rissech et al. 2001; Mafart, 2005). To have the maximum information possible and precise knowledge of this anatomical area it is important to improve our understanding of the biology and physiology of this complex joint, which can lead to improvements in the current ageing methodologies based on the acetabulum (e.g. Rissech et al. 2006; San-Millán et al. 2016) and provide new data for hip surgery and rehabilitation.

Geometric morphometrics is the study of shape variation and its covariation with other variables (Bookstein, 1991; Dryden & Mardia, 1998), where "shape" describes the geometric properties of an object that are invariant to location, scale, and orientation (Slice, 2005). Geometric morphometrics has developed considerably in recent years (Bookstein et al. 1985; Bookstein, 1991; Reyment, 1991; Dryden & Mardia, 1998; Rohlf, 1999, 2000a,b; Adams et al. 2004; Mitteroecker &

Gunz, 2009; Klingenberg, 2011; Adams & Otárola-Castillo, 2013). It has been shown to be a powerful tool for accurately determining and describing subtle morphological shape changes in human skeletal structures that classical measurements could not record. In fact, the use of landmark-based techniques has rapidly increased in the anthropological and anatomical sciences in the last decade (e.g., Perez et al. 2006; Pretorius et al. 2006; Kimmerle et al. 2008; Bytheway & Ross, 2010; Neubauer et al. 2010; Coquerelle et al. 2011; Harvati & Hublin, 2012; Lycett & von Cramon-Taubadel, 2013; Bastir et al. 2014; San-Millán et al. 2015). However, many areas of biological structures, such as the lunate surface or acetabular fossa of the acetabulum, have few or no identifiable landmarks, as their structure is represented only by surfaces, curves, or outlines (Niewoehner, 2005). In these cases, the methodological problem has been recently overcome through the use of sliding semi-landmarks, which allows for capturing shape variation across the sample (Bookstein, 1997; Bookstein et al. 1999; Adams et al. 2013).

In this study, we present a two-dimensional geometric morphometric analysis of the human acetabulum and its fossa using recently defined landmarks and sliding semi-landmarks (San-Millán et al. 2015). The objective is to assess shape and size differences of the acetabulum related to sex and age. Although the functional implications of acetabular variability have long been identified, this study is the first to use geometric morphometrics to explore the shape and size variation of the human acetabulum and its fossa across the entire adult life span.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Osteological material

We analysed a total of 682 individuals (327 ♀, 355 ♂), coming from three modern documented skeletal collections: (1) Madrid collection (San-Millán et al. 2013), housed in the School of Legal Medicine at the Faculty of Medicine of the Complutense University of Madrid (Madrid, Spain); (2) Valladolid collection (Pastor et al. 1995), housed in the Anatomical Museum at the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Valladolid (Valladolid, Spain); (3) Lisbon collection (Cardoso, 2006), housed in the Museo Bocage of Lisbon (National Museum of Natural History, Lisbon, Portugal). The Madrid and Valladolid collections comprise individuals who died in the 20th century while the specimens of the Lisbon collection died between the end of the 19th and the end of the 20th centuries. The three skeletal collections used in this research come from three different geographical regions of the Iberian Peninsula. They were chosen in order to include a representative sample of different regions of the Iberian population, taking into account their availability and their potentially large age ranges. All of these collections are derived from modern cemeteries and have documented demographic information, and records of birth and death are available. Further information

concerning the three Iberian collections can be found in a range of publications (i.e. Pastor et al. 1995; Cardoso, 2006; Rissech & Steadman, 2010; Rissech et al. 2012; Ruíz et al. 2012; San-Millán et al. 2013).

Individuals with mature acetabula (completely fused) were selected in order to cover the entire period of acetabular maturity. In our sample, the complete fusion of the acetabulum occurs at 15 years in males and at 12 years in females (Rissech et al. 2003; Rissech & Malgosa, 2005, 2007), which is in accordance with the given standard intervals for acetabular maturity (14-17 y. ♂; 11-15 y. ♀) in the current population (Scheuer & Black, 2000). In order to create the same age intervals in both sexes, we chose exclusively individuals with fused acetabula 15 years of age and older. Thus our sample has an age range from 15 to 101 years. Table 1 presents detailed information regarding the age, sex and collection of the individuals analysed in this study.

The left os coxa, without any pathology and/or deformity that might affect the analysis, was chosen from each individual. We included individuals with non-inflammatory osteoarthritis or diffuse idiopathic skeletal hyperostosis (DISH) because these conditions are related to age (Cunha, 1996; Schmitt, 2001). In the case of a missing, broken (where the positioning of the complete set of landmarks described subsequently is infeasible) or pathological left os coxa, the right bone was analysed (see below). Furthermore, we excluded fused pelvises (os coxa and sacrum), as it was impossible to maintain our photographic protocol due to the limited space of the box used to position each of the os coxa.

2.2. Photography technique

High-resolution orthogonal photographs of the acetabulum were taken using a Nikon D-3100 digital camera mounted in a fixed position, and equipped with an 18-55 mm objective set at a focal distance of 55 mm. The position and inclination of the camera were fixed using a tripod associated with a spirit level - this instrument indicates whether a surface is horizontal. Following the same protocol used by San-Millán et al. (2015; Appendix 1), the position of the acetabulum was standardized relative to the optical axis of the camera by placing the os coxa in a wooden box filled with packing peanuts. The acetabulum was positioned upwards, with the acetabular rim parallel to the camera lens. The camera was always positioned at a height of 320 mm directly above the acetabular fossa. The opening plane of the acetabulum was defined by three different references: (i) the position of the acetabular fossa with respect to the camera lens and the levelling of the acetabular rim; (ii) the definition of three anatomical points (a, b and c) with respect to metric references of the box (Fig. 1A), which were used to define the vertical and the horizontal axes; and

(iii) the established grid of the camera's screen. The acetabular rim was positioned lying parallel to the ground and the camera lens by a spirit level. Thus, it was first calibrated in the ground and then, it was used to check if the camera lens and the acetabular rim were parallel to the same plane. The bone was placed inside the box with the iliac crest on the top and the pubic symphysis at the left. The vertical midline of the box crossed through point "a" (the most posterior point of the ilium over the acetabular rim just below the anterior border of the ilium) and "b" (the apex of posterior horn) (Fig. 1A). A horizontal line, positioned exactly 11 centimetres from the bottom of the box, passed through point "c" (the apex of anterior horn) (Fig. 1A). Possible ageing osteophytes were not considered at either points "b" or "c". These three anatomical points were used to ensure that each os coxa was correctly positioned within the camera's established grid, visible on the LCD monitor. Additionally, a 10 mm x 20 mm scale was included in each photograph. In the cases where the right os coxae were examined (16.98 % of the total specimens), the protocol was identical, except that the obtained images were mirrored/reflected to obtain a left-oriented os coxa shape. Although some of these procedures may not be required for the implementation of geometric morphometric methods, they minimized digitising error and greatly improved the quality of the shape data obtained.

2.3. Landmarks and semi-landmarks

Two bi-dimensional landmarks and thirty-two sliding semi-landmarks (Fig. 1B) were digitised using tpsDig2 (Rohlf, 2010) following the protocol outlined by San-Millán et al. (2015) completely surrounding the lunate surface of the acetabulum. Landmarks 1 and 2 were placed in the apex of the anterior and posterior acetabular horns of the lunate surface respectively (Fig. 1B). Both landmarks are considered Type II (Bookstein, 1991) or mathematical (Dryden & Mardia, 1998) since they are recorded as the maxima of curvature of both acetabular horns. Furthermore, they were positioned in accordance with possible age-related osteophytes (Rissech et al. 2006). The remaining thirty-two sliding semi-landmarks were evenly spaced across the acetabular rim and the outer edge of the acetabular fossa, surrounding the entire lunate surface, and were automatically obtained in TpsDig2. This program allows the contour of the lunate surface to be defined with a continuous trace, which was initiated at landmark 1 and finished at landmark 2 (Fig. 1B)

After digitising landmarks and semi-landmarks, Procrustes-based geometric morphometrics (Rohlf & Slice, 1990; Bookstein, 1991) was used to obtain shape variables for statistical analyses. A Generalized Procrustes Analysis (GPA: Rohlf & Slice, 1990) was performed to superimpose all specimens into a common location, and remove the effects of size and orientation from landmark coordinates. During superimposition, a Procrustes relaxation procedure was used, where semi-landmarks were allowed to slide, in order to minimize Procrustes distances across specimens

(Bookstein 1997; Gunz et al. 2005). This removed all tangential variation along the curves (Perez et al. 2006). Then, the coordinates of the superimposed configurations were orthogonally projected to tangent space, in order to achieve shape variables for the statistical analyses. Procrustes superimposition and projection to tangent space were performed using the *gpagen* function of *geomorph* R-package (Adams & Otárola-Castillo, 2013).

To avoid confusion, we used a clock-wise orientation for spatial descriptions of the acetabulum following the protocol of Köhnlein et al. (2009) (Fig. 1C). To this end, the protocol-based digitised images were mirrored/reflected and rotated to match this specific clinical clock-wise orientation, modifying the orientation of the acetabula from Figure 1B to Figure 1C. The 180° meridian (6:00) line was positioned over the midpoint of the acetabular notch and thirty-six reference points in 10° increments along the rim were marked (Fig. 1C). In the cases where there was extensive bone growth on one or both acetabular horns, the osteophytes were not considered.

Measurement errors are an important source of variation affecting morphometric data that can increase the likelihood of type II errors and lead to biased results (Arnqvist & Martensson, 1998). In the present study we followed the protocol of our previous study on human and non-human primate acetabulum (San-Millán et al. 2015), in which we exhaustively analysed intra and inter-observer error introduced during photographic process, positioning of the bone and digitising landmarks (San-Millán et al. 2015; Appendix 2). Taking into account the results obtained in this previous study and the fact that the analysis was undertaken by the same person (M. S-M.), the measurement error during the photographic process, and bone and the landmark positioning were considered negligible.

2.4. Data analysis

With the intention to explore acetabular size, as centroid size variation between the different age groups and sexes, a resampling ANOVA with sex and age groups as factors was performed based on 1,000 permutations of Euclidean distance matrices, as implemented by the function *adonis* of the *vegan* R-package (Oksanen et al. 2012). The age groups considered in this study were: 1) 15-39 years old (Females: n=66, mean=26.86; Males: n=90, mean=28.37); 2) 40-64 years old (Females: n=104, mean=52.61; Males: n=138 mean=51.74) and 3) older than 65 years old (Females: n=157, mean=78.62; Males: n=127, mean=76.65). These three age ranges have been chosen following the morphological stages of the acetabulum described by Calce (2012) - young adults, middle-aged adults and old adults. Use of these three age ranges is further supported by the fact that results using these broad ranges were the same as those obtained considering individual chronological ages. The broad

age ranges offer the advantage of allowing more accurate observation of morphological age changes due to the large quantity of data. We used a resampling ANOVA due to the high dimensionality of shape data and the varied sample size among the age-groups considered (Anderson & Ter Braak, 2003).

Since differences in acetabular size among sex-age groups could potentially influence shape variation, the influence of allometry on shape variation across age groups and sex series was evaluated. A Procrustes MANOVA on shape was performed, with centroid size, sex, and age group as factors, as implemented in the `procD.lm` function of the `geomorph` R-package (Adams & Otárola-Castillo, 2013). After examining size variation, and to examine differences in acetabular shape between pairs of sex-age groups, while accounting for shape variation due to centroid size, a pair-wise comparison was performed between groups using the Euclidean distances among group means. Pair-wise comparisons were conducted using the `pairwiseD.test` function of the `geomorph` R-package, designed as a post-hoc test to previous Procrustes MANOVA (Adams & Otárola-Castillo, 2013). Throughout, we corrected p-values for the potential effect of conducting multiple comparisons using the False Discovery Rate procedure (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995; Curran-Everett, 2000).

In order to evaluate possible sex differences in the shape pattern of the acetabulum, a principal components analysis (PCA in shape space or relative warp analysis) was applied in each age interval. This analysis reduces the complex multidimensional data into a few eigenvectors representing linear combinations of the landmark displacements (Zelditch et al. 2004). In the same manner, to evaluate possible age-related changes in acetabular shape, a PCA was performed in each sex. With the aim of displaying shape differences across principal component (PC) axes, the thin plate spline was used to create deformation grids (Bookstein, 1991, 1996; Rohlf, 1996), using the `plotRefToTarget` function of the `geomorph` R-package (Adams & Otárola-Castillo, 2013). Furthermore, with the same function, we generated additional, larger plots based on vectors of deformation to show the exact position, direction and magnitude of the sex- and age-based shape differences (i.e., to improve visualisation). These plots represent the shape difference between the consensus form (mean shape) of a target specimen relative to a consensus form (mean shape) of a reference specimen through different size vectors. Thus, these graphs do not represent the mean of the groups, but rather the shape *difference* between pairs of groups: for example, mean shape of 40-65-year-old males compared with mean shape of 40-65-year-old females. Moreover, the magnitude of the scale was exaggerated four times relative to the observed data range, to facilitate visualisation of the results.

Lastly, due to the observation in some of the specimens analysed of a clover-leaf shape of the acetabular fossa with one of the lobes clearly elongated (see the Results section), Chi squared analyses were used to determine the possible existence of significant differences in the number of cases of this morphological variant in the outer edge of the acetabular fossa among age groups and sexes separately.

All statistical analyses were performed using the R language for statistical computing (R Core Team, 2013).

3. RESULTS

Results in resampling ANOVA on centroid size with sex and age groups as factors (Table 2) indicated that acetabular size differed significantly between males and females but not among age groups. In addition, the effect of the interaction sex x age on size was not significant (Table 2).

The resampling MANOVA test on shape, performed to evaluate possible allometric effects, suggested that acetabular size, sex and age group have a significant effect on the acetabular shape variation (Table 3). Nevertheless, size influence on shape was uniform between males and females (no significant interaction between centroid size and sex), and among age groups (no significant interaction between centroid size and age group) (Table 3). Interestingly, the ageing shape pattern was shared by both sexes (no significant interaction between age group and sex) (Table 3).

Pair-wise comparisons of the acetabular shape between sexes taking into account age groups (post-hoc test to the previous resampling MANOVA) indicated the presence of significant acetabular shape differences between males and females younger than 65 years of age (Table 4).

Figure 2A shows the distribution of the male and female individuals on shape space in the young adult group. The first two components (PC1 and PC2) explained 48.8% of the total variation (PC1: 30.9%; PC2: 17.9%). The shape changes associated with the increase in PC1 score were diminution of the acetabular fossa and increase of the lunate surface. The shape change related to the increase in PC2 score was diminution of the acetabular notch width. Thus, males seem to have relatively smaller acetabular fossa size and acetabular notch width compared to females. Figure 2B shows the distribution of the males and females on shape space in middle-aged group. The first two components explained 56.7% of the total variation (PC1: 39.3%; PC2: 17.3%). In this age group, the same shape differences as that of the previous age group were observed between sexes, although there was a greater overlap in the sex distribution. Figure 2C shows the distribution of sex on shape space in the aged-adults group. The first two components explained 61.7% of the total variation

(PC1: 37.6%; PC2: 24.1%). In this case, the overlap in the sex distribution was almost complete, although females seem to present higher shape variability along PC1, and males present it along PC2. As in the two previous age groups, PC1 essentially described changes in the acetabular fossa and lunate surface size while PC2 principally reflected changes in the acetabular notch width. Figures 2D, 2E and 2F are plots based on vector deformation, showing acetabular shape differences between sexes when age group is taken into account. This is visualised as deformation diagrams based on the female and male consensus forms of each age interval by thin-plate spine methods. The positions of landmarks in the reference shape (in this case, female shape) are shown as grey dots and the shifts of landmarks to the target shape (in this case, male shape) are indicated by deformation vectors. These vectors indicate the direction and magnitude of the morphological differences between males in relation to females. These results indicate that males had a relatively extended acetabular rim (especially from 10:00 to 1:00), a narrower acetabular notch, and a more reduced acetabular fossa size. This was observed throughout adult life span - although only significantly in individuals younger than 65 years old. This means that men have a larger lunate surface than females.

Hereafter, due to the presence of significant acetabular shape differences between males and females, the evaluation of the possible age-related changes in acetabular shape was done separately for males and females.

Pair-wise comparisons of acetabular shape between the three age groups taken into account sex, using the Euclidean distances among group means as a post-hoc test to previous Procrustes MANOVA (Table 3), indicated significant differences among all cases (Table 4).

The first two PCs of shape variation among the entire female sample (Fig. 3A), explained 60.7% of the total variation (PC1: 41.3%; PC2: 19.4%). On the other hand, the first two PCs of shape variation across the entire male sample taking into account age (Fig. 4A), explained 54.9% of the total variation (PC1: 33.9%; PC2: 21.0%). The distribution of the different individuals in the shape space showed that acetabular shape varied progressively according to age in both sexes. Results also indicated that acetabular shape variability increases with age in males and females, which also experienced a similar pattern of age-related shape changes (Fig. 3A vs. Fig. 4A). In both sexes, the first component mainly reflected changes in the acetabular fossa and lunate surface size. On the other hand, PC2 primarily described changes in the acetabular notch width and global acetabular morphology, either more elliptical or more circular. As previously, shape differences between age groups taking into account sex were represented by deformation vectors plots, where location and size of the vectors indicate the exact position, direction and magnitude of age-related shape differences (Fig. 3B and Fig. 4B) of the target group (in this case, the older group analysed) in relation to the reference group (in this case, the younger group analysed). The observation of these plots

shows that, in both sexes, the age-related acetabular shape differences were mainly characterised by 1) the acetabular profiles to become modified (this change consisted of an extension along 10:00 to 1:00 section, and a reduction of around 7:00 to 9:00 area); 2) the tendency of the acetabular notches to gradually narrow; and 3) the acetabular fossae to experience a reduction in size (Fig. 3B and Fig. 4B).

Additionally, our observations indicated that in both sexes, the acetabular fossa extended towards the lunate surface in three specific directions, around 9:00, around 1:00 and around 4:00 (Arrows in Figs. 3C and 4C), forming three lobes. Thus, there was a recognizable clover-leaf shape of the acetabular fossae. This shape pattern is visible especially in younger individuals (arrows in Figs. 3C and 4C and Fig. 5) and tends to be less marked with age, becoming nearly rounded in older individuals (Figs. 3C and 4C). The lobe situated around 1:00 is the best defined and is located in the acetabular area of the ilium. The lobe placed around 4:00 is situated in the pubic area, between the acetabular and ilio-pubic notches; and the lobe visible around 9:00 is found in the ischium, between the acetabular and ilio-ischial notches. In some cases, the 1:00-lobe appeared particularly elongated, almost crossing the lunate surface (arrows in Fig. 6). In our sample this feature was more frequently present in the youngest age group (males, 6.7%; females, 14.9%), in relation to middle aged adults (males: 3.6%; females: 5.8%) and older adults (males: 0.0%; females: 2.6%). Thereby, in the current sample, this trait was found significantly more often in younger individuals, both in males ($X^2= 8.004$; $p=0.018^*$) and females ($X^2= 12.504$; $p=0.002^*$). However, although the elongated 1:00-lobe appeared more frequently in females than in males in every age group, these differences were not significant (15-39 years old: $X^2=2.862$; $p=0.091$; 40-64 years old: $X^2=0.630$; $p=0.428$; > 65 years old: $X^2=3.303$; $p=0.069$).

4. DISCUSSION

This is the first study in which the shape of the mature human acetabulum and its fossa have been analysed in detail, considering acetabular size, sex and age. It is a descriptive study based on Geometric morphometrics and associated statistical analyses. The data presented provide anatomical information and identify shape and size differences of the acetabulum related to sex and age that complement previous information on this anatomical element. As expected, results revealed that the male acetabulum was, in absolute values, larger than the female acetabulum, which is in accordance with current published research (e.g. Genovés, 1959; Rissech & Malgosa, 1997; Murphy, 2000; Albanese, 2003; Benazzi et al. 2008; Köhnlein et al. 2009; Macaluso, 2011). Furthermore, and based on our results, the influence that size has on shape was uniform between sexes, and among age groups. Neither sex nor age had a significant effect on the size-shape relationship, which

supported a common allometric pattern that is independent of these two factors. Although This could be explained by biomechanical factors related to direct restrictions on bipedalism, the results of San-Millán et al. (2015) regarding the existence of a common allometric pattern shared by the different locomotor groups in primates make a high constraint at the level of phylogenetic order a reasonable explanation. However, further specific research into this allometric relationship in higher taxonomic levels or other groups would be advisable.

4.1. Acetabular shape differences related to sex

The acetabular shape differences associated with sex were significant even after removing possible allometric effects. Among these differences those related to the lunate surface and acetabular fossa shape were the most significant (extension of the outer rim profile, acetabular notch width and acetabular fossa area). This is in accordance with the observations of Köhnlein et al. (2009), who found similar acetabular shape differences between sexes. The Köhnlein et al. study was based on a Swiss sample dating from the Early Middle Age (6th to 13th centuries) consisting of 33 individuals, between 18 and 60 years of age, with no-coxoarthrosis. According to these authors, the sex-based acetabular shape differences in the acetabulum were related to the size of the lunate surface and acetabular fossa and width of the acetabular notch rather than the outer rim profile. Although the reasons for these sex-based acetabular shape differences are unknown, they seem to be related to both individual robusticity, and femoral shape which in turn is related to the pelvis width. The observed sex-based acetabular shape differences make the articular surface relatively larger in males than in females, which is in agreement with the fact that males usually exhibit more robust bones with well-developed articular areas and muscular attachments, because of their greater weight and muscular strength. On the other hand, acetabular morphology is also directly related to femoral shape and orientation within the hip joint, which show well-known sex differences. Femoral morphology is also related to the birth canal which in turn can partially (and indirectly) determine the acetabular shape. Both neck–shaft and bicondylar angles are related to the development of the pelvic width (Pujol et al. 2014, 2015), specifically with the bi-acetabular and transverse diameter of the mid-plane of the pelvis (Kurki, 2013; Crespo et al. 2015). The relatively broader bicondylar angle in females (Igbigbi & Sharrif, 2005; Pandya et al. 2008; Pujol et al. 2014, 2015), and narrower neck–shaft angle (Gómez-Alonso et al. 2000; Igbigbi, 2003; Bernard et al. 2012; Pujol et al. 2015) determine the position of the hip joint and probably part of the acetabular shape.

In spite of these significant acetabular shape differences between sexes in young adult and middle aged adult groups, there remained great overlap in the sex distribution of the individuals when PCA plots were performed. This overlap makes it difficult to identify an unknown individual as

man or woman inside the distribution. This indicates that probably the acetabular and fossa shape are not useful for adult sex estimation. However, before to stating this with certainty it should be tested in different samples.

Our results on sex-related acetabular shape differences call into question the opinion of some authors (Rougé-Maillart et al. 2007, 2009; Calce, 2012) who think that age progression changes in acetabulum are related only to age, not to sex. This is further called into question when we take into account the observations of Mays (2012), San-Millán (2015) and San-Millán et al. (2016) who found a slower rate of acetabular ageing in females compared to males. These differences between sexes agree with the well-known higher predisposition to bone production in males than in females (Resnick & Niwayama, 1983; Rogers et al. 1997; Schneider et al. 2002; Rogers et al. 2004; Schmitt et al. 2007). All of this appears to suggest that adult skeletal age estimation based on the acetabulum would be more accurate if we estimated age-at-death taking into account sex.

4.2. Acetabular shape differences related to age

The results obtained in this study allowed us to describe the variation in shape of the male and female acetabulum due to age. With age, a relative masculinization was observed in the shape of the acetabulum and the acetabular fossa. In other words, as individuals of both sexes aged, there was a tendency to: (i) modify the acetabular rim profile; (ii) narrow the acetabular notch; and (iii) reduce the acetabular fossa size. These three age-related changes are associated with bone proliferation in three specific anatomical regions of the acetabulum: the acetabular rim, the acetabular horns, and the outer edge of the acetabular fossa.

The morphological changes of the acetabular rim profile related to age are linked to chondro-osteophytosis along the acetabular rim, that occurs during the ageing process, and is discussed in detail in previous literature mainly related to adult age estimation based on the acetabulum (Rissech, 2001; Rougé-Maillart et al. 2004; Rissech et al. 2006, 2007; Rougé-Maillart et al. 2007, 2009; Calce & Rogers, 2011; Bonneau et al. 2012; Calce, 2012; Mays, 2012; San-Millán et al. 2016). The variance found in the rim profile is due to orientation differences in osteophytic growth throughout the acetabular rim. Growth usually occurs leaning slightly toward the lunate surface around the 8:00 rim region, while moving outwards in the outermost portion of the rim, especially from 10:00 to 1:00 (Arrows in Fig. 7A, B, C). One of the factors influencing bone production in the acetabular rim is the presence of age-dependent changes in the cartilage from physiological joint stress throughout life (Noguchi et al. 1999). These changes appear to be partially triggered by femoro-acetabular impingement (Leunig et al. 2003). The bone production on the acetabular rim

influences the overall acetabular shape, becoming relatively wider in the anterior-posterior axis with increased ageing. This is important for arthroplasty procedures, where the age group of the patient should be considered to minimise joint injury related to the absence congruency between bones and orthopaedic replacements.

Morphological changes in the acetabular notch with age are related to enthesophytosis of the transvers ligament, in conjunction with the production of marginal osteophytes (chondro-osteophytosis) around the horns of the lunate surface, particularly on the posterior horn (arrow in Fig. 7D). In some cases, this bone growth may almost (arrow in Fig. 7E) or completely cross the acetabular notch (arrows in Fig. 7F) and also include activity on the anterior horn (arrowheads in Fig. 7E, F). These changes are in accordance with the studies that use the apex activity of the posterior horn of the lunate surface of the acetabulum, as a variable for adult age estimation (Rougé-Maillart et al. 2004; Rissech et al. 2006, 2007; Rougé-Maillart et al. 2007, 2009; Calce & Rogers, 2011; Calce, 2012; Mays, 2012; San-Millán et al. 2016).

The morphological changes on the outer edge of the fossa due to age are related to osteophytic growth both on the outer edge of the acetabular fossa parallel to the fossa and in the fossa itself (Fig. 8). Although results from samples from Canada (Calce & Rogers, 2011) and England (Mays, 2012) questioned the correlation between age and osteophytic growth on the outer edge of the acetabular fossae (related to variables 5-7 of Rissech's (2006) adult age estimation method), the current results from the Iberian sample confirmed this age-related bone production which was found in samples from Western Europe (Rissech et al. 2006, 2007), Japan and Singapore (Noguchi et al. 1999) and Colombia (Rissech, 2013). According to Noguchi et al. (1999), the reduction of the fossa size begins with a decrease of the fibro-fatty pulvinar tissue of the fossa, followed by the gradual appearance of marginal chondro-osteophytes. This growth in the fossa or on the lunate surface inwards can eventually occupy the entire fossa resulting in its total obliteration.

The results of this study are consistent with the age-change progression defined in the acetabular method proposed by Rissech et al. (2006) in males, specifically for variables 2 (acetabular rim shape), 4 (apex activity) and 5 (activity of the outer edge of the acetabular fossa). These results, which support San-Millán et al. (2016) observations, increase the applicability of the male-specific method of Rissech et al. (2006) to include females, at least for variables that involve osteophyte development. Furthermore, these observations also agree with the well-established age-related marginal bone growth recorded on the other two pelvic joints (pubic symphysis and auricular surface), which are widely used in classic adult age estimation techniques (e.g. Todd, 1920; Lovejoy et al. 1985; Katz & Suchey, 1986; Brooks & Suchey, 1990; Buckberry & Chamberlain, 2002). Acetabular shape variability increases with age, as part of a regular biological process (Figs. 3A and

4A). Increasing variability with age was expected, as it is well documented in the literature with respect to other adult and sub-adult age markers (e.g. Hoffman, 1979; Hens et al. 2008; Rissech et al. 2012, 2013; San-Millán et al. 2013). This is known as the Trajectory Effect (Nawrocki, 2010), and it is what makes adult ageing methods little accurate. In addition, the variability observed in the ageing process in the different adult age markers is also probably linked to the wide individual variation present in osteophyte proliferation (Tsurumoto et al. 2013).

Bone production is a complex and not fully understood process, which seems to occur based on a mixture of systemic -sex, age, metabolic and endocrine factors, nutrition, osteoporosis, vascular perfusion and genetic predisposition- and local factors -functional and biomechanical stress, obesity, severe trauma, and climate (Jurmain, 1977; Weiss & Jurmain, 2007). Periarticular osteophytes emerge through the endochondral ossification of fibrous cartilage at the synovial bone-cartilage junction, and grow gradually throughout an individual's lifetime as age-related phenomena (Tsurumoto et al. 2013). The similarities between sex-based acetabular shape differences and the acetabular shape pattern of ageing observed in this study are probably related to the fact that males and older individuals produce relatively more bone than females and younger ones (Rogers et al. 2004). In fact, as discussed above, the increased ability of males to produce more bone than females is well documented (Resnick & Niwayama, 1983; Rogers et al. 1997; Schmitt et al. 2007), and has been noted specifically in both the hip joint (Tsurumoto et al. 2013) and sacro-iliac joint (Sashin, 1930). Additionally, bone production is enhanced in older individuals from physiological reactions to pathological conditions, such as osteoarthritis (Tsurumoto et al. 2013), and because a bone growth persists by periosteal apposition in some parts of the skeleton (Susanne, 1979). Later in life, and according to our observations, increasing bone growth diminishes and obscures sex-based acetabular shape differences. These later changes in the bone production could explain why there were not any significant sex differences in acetabular shape in individuals older than 65 years of age. This observation agrees with the well-established premise that some variables tend to be less sexually dimorphic in older individuals (Olivier, 1965; McLaughlin & Bruce, 1986; Rissech, 2001; Huseynov et al. 2016).

Regarding the shape of the acetabular fossa, the morphology of the acetabulum has been described as a horse-shoe like articular surface (lunate surface) incompletely surrounding a quadrangular nonarticular surface referred to as the acetabular fossa (Testut & Latarjet, 1975; Aiello & Dean, 1990; Scheuer & Black, 2000). Classical anatomical textbooks do not give further details of acetabular fossa morphology or that of the lunate surface (Thane, 1890; Frazer, 1920; Testut & Latarjet, 1975; Rouviere, 1972; Romanes, 1987; Williams, 1995). However, some authors have considered that the acetabular fossa in adult os coxa has a small cranial lobe disrupting the lunate surface (Perna, 1922; Serra, 1938; Washburn, 1948; Gaillard, 1961; Seidler, 1978; Das et al. 1985;

Arsuaga, 1990) and more recently Rissech et al. (2001) described the fossa as a clover leaf-shape with three lobes: anterior, superior and posterior (4:0; 1:0 and 9:0 according our study). Our results confirm the presence of these three lobes described by Rissech et al. (2001), disrupting the lunate surface from the acetabular fossa. The superior lobe (1:0) is the best defined and is located in the acetabular area of the ilium. The anterior lobe (4:0) is situated in the pubic area, between the acetabular and ilio-pubic notches; and the posterior lobe (9:0) is found in the ischium, between the acetabular and ilio-ischial notches (Rissech et al. 2001). Furthermore, in some cases the superior lobe (1:00) is particularly elongated (arrow in Fig. 9A), almost crossing the lunate surface, coinciding with Arsuaga's (1990) observations. Our morphometric results about the clover-leaf shape of the acetabular fossa clearly support the data obtained by Rissech et al. (2001). This fact is more significant if we take into account that the methodology applied in this study captured the clover-leaf morphology described above, despite the fact that the procedure followed only digitised sliding semi-landmarks along the line bordering the acetabular fossa and used only the acetabular horns as landmarks. By following this procedure, no preliminary assumptions on its particular shape were made on acetabular shape, in order to describe its morphology objectively; thus, anatomically significant references were ruled out as landmarks, i.e. any anatomical acetabular point (Rissech et al. 2001) or any of the intersection points between lobes. Although there is not a clear explanation for the consistent presence of these three lobes, they are suggestive of the attachment form of the ligament teres described in foetal specimens (Boucher, 1957).

In addition to and in accordance with the Rissech's et al (2001) observations, our results also indicated that with ageing, the outer edge of the acetabular fossa has a tendency to gradually lose its clover-leaf morphology, becoming more rounded and increasing its shape variability. This ageing pattern could be partially explained by the osteophytic growth commented on above along the outer edge and in the fossa itself, making the limit between the acetabular fossa and the lunate surface more circular or irregular.

With reference to the particularly elongated 1:00-lobe (arrow in Fig. 9A), in our sample, it was found significantly more frequent in males and females from the youngest age group than those from the middle and oldest groups. This is probably related to the major age-related changes that occurred around the superior lobe (1:00 lobe) in the 12:00 to 2:00 area of the outer edge of the acetabular fossa in both sexes (Figs. 3B and 4B). The age-related reduction of the fossa with the resulting partial or total obliteration of the particularly elongated 1:00-lobe might explain the existence of the acetabular crease described by Mafart (2005). This author described the acetabular crease as an indentation delineated by oblique and vertical edges situated above the superior lobe of the fossa (arrow in Fig. 9B). Although Mafart (2005) does not relate the acetabular crease with age, it has never been analysed in detail with documented material. Arsuaga (1990) already postulated that

this crease may be all that is left of the elongated superior lobe that has subsequently been obliterated by acetabular ageing changes. Accordingly, this research appears to support Arsuaga's (1990) claim. Additionally, some cases appear to support this hypothesis, showing age-related partial obliteration of the fossa (white arrows in Fig. 9C, D), while maintaining a slight residual mark (black arrows in Fig. 9C, D) from the original elongated 1:00-lobe (arrowhead in Fig. 9C, D). The acetabular crease described by Mafart (2005) in dry bone could be associated with the presence of the stellate crease observed in fresh cadavers and living individuals. This morphological variant consists of a stellate-appearing normal focus of cartilage absence or thinning specifically around 1:00 (Keene & Villar, 1994; Byrd, 2012; Anderson et al. 2013; Philippon et al. 2014). This feature has been proposed (Byrd, 2006; 2012) to represent a residual scar left after obliteration of the supra-acetabular fossa, another normal developmental variant defined by a bony recess seen in teenagers and young adults at the same acetabular area. The configuration of a tiny fossa above the proper acetabular fossa forms a complex that has been described as a keyhole (Byrd, 2012). According to our age-related findings, the latter trait could be linked to our description and location of the elongated 1:00-lobe (Fig. 6). This biomechanical and anatomical discussion generated by the acetabular crease (Marfart, 2005) and our general lack of knowledge related to the clover leaf-shape of the fossa, which is extremely significant for the anatomical acetabular point (junction of the ilium, ischium and pubic bones) localisation, illustrates the complexity and our poor understanding of the acetabular region (and other adult age markers such as the pubic symphysis and auricular surface).

The results of this study regarding age-related acetabular shape data agree with the age-change progression defined in different adult age-at-death estimation methods based on the acetabulum (Rissech et al. 2006; Rougé-Maillart et al. 2007, 2009; Calce, 2012; San-Millán et al. 2016) and with the observations made by Rissech et al. (2001) on the acetabular development in the postnatal period. The present study indicates that on overall acetabular shape, the ageing pattern observed in this anatomical element was similar and followed comparable trends in both sexes, suggesting that the same specific acetabular variables can be applied in males and females when Rissech's method is applied in a sample. However, because the evidence that females have a slower rate of acetabular ageing compared to males (Mays, 2012; San-Millán, 2015; San-Millán et al. 2016), in conjunction with our significant findings about acetabular shape differences between sexes and the well-known higher predisposition to bone production in males (Resnick & Niwayama, 1983; Rogers et al. 1997; Schneider et al. 2002; Rogers et al. 2004; Schmitt et al. 2007) indicate that adult skeletal age estimation based on the acetabulum would be more accurate if we estimated age-at-death taking into account sex. In other words, we can use the same acetabular variables for males and females; however, because of the differences observed in the rate of ageing between sexes - which can modify the frequency of specific features- it is advisable to use sex-specific reference

samples. We mean, to use a male reference sample for estimating the age at death in a male test sample, and to use a female reference sample for estimating the age in a female test sample.

To compare our results on the acetabulum with those of the pubic symphysis and auricular surface and other adult age markers would be interesting. However, the present study is the first that analyses in-depth and in a detailed manner the human acetabular and fossa shape taking into account age and sex. This line of research is fundamental to maximise the accuracy of the methodologies to achieve better results both in archaeological and forensic contexts. Thus, specific studies on the biology and physiology of the adult age markers, such as this one about the acetabulum, are essential to the improvement of the age estimation techniques. In fact, before the widespread application of any adult age-at-death estimation method, in-depth research about age marker biology and linked factors must be undertaken.

Concluding remarks

Overall morphological changes have been characterised for the human acetabulum and its fossa, as they relate to sex and age. Sex-based differences indicated that males have relatively extended acetabular rim profiles from 10:00 to 1:00, narrower acetabular notches, and reduced acetabular fossae, when compared to females. With age, in females the acetabular shape becomes more similar to the males ones and in the elderly the acetabular shape are far less noticeable between the two sexes. These age-related changes can be explained by the production of marginal osteophytes throughout the acetabular rim and the outer edge of the acetabular fossa and by enthesophytosis on both horns of the lunate surface which correspond to the calcification of the transverse ligament. It should be noted that osteophytic growth is part of the normal process of development/senescence of the joints; thus, it should be considered more physiological than pathological. This similar ageing pattern in both sexes suggests that the same specific acetabular variables can be applied in males and females when Rissech's method is applied in a sample. However, because of the acetabular shape differences and the differences observed in the rate of ageing between sexes, it is advisable to use sex-specific reference samples. Our observations also indicate that in cases of replacements surgery the age group of the patient should be considered to minimise joint injury related to the absence congruency between the acetabulum and the prosthesis.

The anatomical description of the acetabulum, the precise understanding of the acetabular shape and how it changes depending on age and sex, have implications in biological anthropology. The results are important in forming a basis for the development of age-estimation techniques, which are essential for osteology, bioarchaeology, forensic anthropology and legal medicine. In

addition, in a clinical sense, precise knowledge of acetabular morphology is also important for surgical procedures and a more realistic design of acetabular implants.

This study also highlights the relevance of geometric morphometric methods in capturing subtle shape differences that conventional methods cannot detect. This work is the first which attempts to assess acetabular shape variation in humans considering both sex and age. However, due to the digitisation limitations in quantifying the shape of a three dimensional structure through 2D procedures, it would be desirable to reproduce this analysis with 3D shape-data for more accurate representation and understanding of the native morphology of the acetabulum in different sex-age groups.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. A) Reference points used in the photographic protocol. B) Location of the digitised landmarks (1 and 2) and sliding semi-landmarks (3 - 34) used to quantify acetabular shape. C) The acetabular rim, outer edge of the acetabular fossa, and overall lunate surface locations are indicated in a rotated and reflected/mirrored clockwise distribution from 1:00 to 12:00 following Köhnlein et al. (2009). Landmarks 1 (LM 1: anterior horn of the lunate surface) and 2 (LM 2: posterior horn of the lunate surface) are represented by red points to better visualisation.

Figure 2. A-C) PCA plots for visualising shape variation between sexes in each age group. The ellipses include 95% confidence intervals of the means (group centroids) of the female sample analysed. Deformation grids at the four sides of the scatterplot represent the extreme shapes observed for the PC1 and PC2 axes. D-F) Graphs illustrating through deformation vectors the shape differences observed between females (reference, in gray points) to males (target, in black dashed line) in the different age groups. Scale has been exaggerated four times relative to the observed data range, to facilitate visualisation.

Figure 3. A) PCA plot for visualising shape variation among all female age groups. The ellipses include 95% confidence intervals of the means (group centroids) of the female sample analysed. Deformation grids at the four sides of the scatterplot represent the extreme shapes observed for the PC1 and PC2 axes. B) Graphs representing through deformation vectors the pair-wise shape differences observed between the different female age groups. Reference group (younger) is shown in gray points and target group (older), in black dashed line. Scale has been exaggerated four times relative to the observed data range, to facilitate visualisation. C) Point graphs represent the mean acetabular shape for the three different female age groups. Arrows indicate the three lobes of the clover-leaf shape of the outer edge of the acetabular fossa in the younger group, where they are more evident.

Figure 4. A) PCA plot for visualising shape variation among all male age groups. The ellipses include 95% confidence intervals of the means (group centroids) of the male sample analysed. Deformation grids at the four sides of the scatterplot represent the extreme shapes observed for the PC1 and PC2 axes. B) Graphs representing through deformation vectors the pair-wise shape differences observed between the different male age groups. Reference group (younger) is shown in gray points and target group (older), in black dashed line. Scale has been exaggerated four times relative to the observed data range, to facilitate visualisation. C) Point graphs represent the mean acetabular shape for the three different male age groups. Arrows indicate the three lobes of the clover-leaf shape of the outer edge of the acetabular fossa in the younger group, where they are more evident.

Figure 5. Different examples of typical clover-leaf acetabular fossa shape. Arrows indicate the different lobes identified. A) Male, 18 years old. B) Male, 44 years old. C) Female, 25 years old. Bar scale (white line) represents 1 centimetre.

Figure 6. Different examples of the elongated expression of the 1:00-lobe, indicated by an arrow. A) Female, 18 years old. B) Female, 26 years old. C) Female, 23 years old. Bar scale (white line) represents 1 centimetre.

Figure 7. Morphological differences as a result of the ageing process located on the acetabular rim profile (top) and the acetabular notch (bottom). A) Male, 83 years old. B) Female, 56 years old. C) Female, 94 years old. A-C show different examples of the acetabular rim modification due to the

orientation of the age-related osteophytic growth on it. The general ageing pattern observed (arrows) consists of bone growth which usually occurs leaning slightly toward the lunate surface around the 8:00 rim region, while moving outwards in the outermost portion of the rim, especially from 10:00 to 1:00. Bar scale (white line) represents 1 centimetre. D) Female, 73 years old. E) Male, 83 years old. F) Male, 67 years old. D-F show different examples of the osteophytic expression on the posterior acetabular horn of different size (arrows), almost (E) or completely crossing (F) the acetabular notch. In E-F, arrowheads indicate bone proliferation on the anterior horn.

Figure 8. Different examples of the acetabular fossa reduction in size due to bone growth (arrows) both in the outer edge of the acetabular fossa, parallel to it, and in the fossa itself. A) Male, 71 years old. Arrows indicate bone proliferation slight in size, but along the outer edge of the acetabular fossa. B) Female, 77 years old. C) Female, 92 years old; D) Male, 57 years old; E) Female, 87 years old; F) Female, 96 years old. B-F show different examples of fossa reduction in size due to age-related bone proliferation on the outer edge of the acetabular fossa. Bar scale (white line) represents 1 centimetre.

Figure 9. A) Male, 46 years old. Arrow indicates the presence of the elongated 1:00-lobe. B) Male, 55 years old. Arrow indicates the presence of the acetabular crease. C) Male, 89 years old. D) Female, 81 years old. In C-D, arrowheads indicate the residual of an elongated 1:00-lobe which have been obliterated and partially erased by age-related bone growth (white arrows), leaving an evident mark (black arrows). Bar scale (white line) represents 1 centimetre.

Figure 1
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Figure 2
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Figure 3
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A

B

C

Figure 4
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A

B

Males 40-64 years
Males 15-39 years

Males > 65 years
Males 15-29 years

Males > 65 years
Males 40-64 years

C

15-39 years

40-64 years

> 65 years

Figure 5
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Figure 6
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Figure 7
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TABLES

Table 1. Distribution of specimens by sex, age and collection. UVA: Valladolid collection; UCM: Madrid collection; LISBOA: Lisbon collection.

	UVA		UCM		LISBOA		TOTAL	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
15-19 years	0	0	0	0	12	13	12	13
20-29 years	1	0	7	3	24	25	32	28
30-39 years	4	1	19	9	23	15	46	25
40-49 years	8	3	18	9	29	20	55	32
50-59 years	15	3	23	4	20	46	58	53
60-69 years	17	12	5	9	30	28	52	49
70-79 years	15	14	13	21	23	20	51	55
80-89 years	17	16	9	17	21	21	47	54
90-99 years	0	5	2	2	0	10	2	17
> 100 years	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total	77	55	96	74	182	198	355	327
	132		170		380		682	

Table 2. Results of resampling ANOVA on centroid size with age group and sex as factors. DF: degrees of freedom, SS: sums of squares, MS: mean squares, p: corresponding p-value. Significant differences are marked in bold. The level of significance is $p \leq 0.001$.

	DF	SS	MS	p
Age group	2	2.22	1.112	0.130
Sex	1	310.78	310.773	0.001
Age group x sex	2	2.19	1.097	0.134
Residuals	676	375.68	0.556	
Total	681	690.88		

Table 3. Results of resampling MANOVA on shape with centroid size, sex and age group as factors.

DF: degrees of freedom, SS: sums of squares, MS: mean squares, p: corresponding p-value. Significant differences are marked in bold. The level of significance is $p \leq 0.001$.

	<i>DF</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>p</i>
<i>Centroid size</i>	1	0.024	0.024	0.001
<i>Sex</i>	1	0.038	0.038	0.001
<i>Age group</i>	2	0.195	0.097	0.001
<i>Centroid size x sex</i>	1	0.005	0.005	0.430
<i>Centroid size x age group</i>	2	0.015	0.007	0.174
<i>Age group x sex</i>	2	0.011	0.005	0.388
<i>Centroid size x age group x sex</i>	2	0.007	0.004	0.736
<i>Residuals</i>	670	3.324	0.005	
<i>Total</i>	681	3.618		

Table 4. P-values obtained from pair-wise comparisons of acetabular shape across sex-age groups, using the Euclidean distances among group means after standardizing shape data for the effects of centroid size, presented as a post-hoc test to previous Procrustes MANOVA (Table 3). False Discovery Rate procedure for correcting p-values for multiple comparisons has been implemented. Significant differences are marked in bold. The level of significance is $p \leq 0.05$.

	<i>Females</i> <i>15-39</i>	<i>Females</i> <i>40-64</i>	<i>Females</i> <i>> 65</i>	<i>Males</i> <i>15-39</i>	<i>Males</i> <i>40-64</i>	<i>Males</i> <i>> 65</i>
<i>Females 15-39</i>	1.000					
<i>Females 40-64</i>	0.005	1.000				
<i>Females > 65</i>	0.002	0.002	1.000			
<i>Males 15-39</i>	0.005			1.000		
<i>Males 40-64</i>		0.029		0.019	1.000	
<i>Males > 65</i>			0.234	0.004	0.004	1.000

Reviewer #1:

This manuscript reports some descriptive data on the shape and size variability in the acetabulum when sex and age is considered. The results derived from a study conducted in three different skeletal collections. In general, it is well written but in my opinion some changes are needed:

The selected article type is Original Research Article I wonder if data population type could fit more.

We believe that the paper is Original Research Article rather than a Data Population Type, because it brings important information on the ageing process of the acetabulum, especially on form changes. These observations come to complement the observation done in our previously study based on acetabular traits and Bayesian approach to estimate adult age. The present paper sheds new light on improving adult age estimation based on the acetabulum.

ABSTRACT:

In the abstract the authors refer to 10:00 and 1:00 and so on but they never mentioned what is localized at 12:00. In this way the reader cannot understand to what they want to refer to. It would be nice if they mention some characteristics related to the well-known anatomical landmarks seen the abstract is an overall presentation of the study and needs to be well understood by anyone, even from who wants just get few information without reading all the text.

We have added more information on the clock-wise landmarks. See the abstract

HIGHLIGHTS:

The second highlight would benefit of some changes in the wording like for example: The acetabulum shape variation highly depends on factors as sex, size and age Again, also for both, the fifth and the fourth highlight, some wording adjustment is necessary.

We have modified them. Now they say:

- 682 acetabula were analysed by geometric morphometrics taken into account sex and age.
- Acetabular shape variation depends on factors as size, sex and age.
- Acetabular fossa has a clover-leaf morphology.
- Males have wider lunate surfaces, narrower notches and smaller fossae than females.
- With age acetabular fossa lose its clover-leaf shape, becoming more rounded.

MATERIAL and METHODS:

This section should be shortened. I am sure that it could benefit in fluency if some parts were synthesized.

In the paragraph 'Section overall differences in acetabular size and shape' I think there is a linguistic error that changes the meaning of the sentence which is repeated often in the results description: it is the shape and the acetabular size that show differences when sex and age are considered and not vice versa. I think that all the results should be rewritten in a clearer way if this is the meaning that the authors want to pass.

The Material and Methods section has been shortened to improve the fluency of the text.

We have also removed the Measurement errors section and this text has been reduced and placed at the end of the Landmarks and semi-landmarks section. In the present study we followed the protocol of our previous study (San-Millán et al., 2015) in which we exhaustively analysed intra and inter observer error. Taking into account the results obtained in this previous study and the fact that the analysis was undertaken for the same author (San-Millán), the

measurement error was considered negligible. All of this has been explained in Material and Methods section. See “Landmarks and semi-landmarks” section.

We also have corrected the linguistic error that changes the meaning of the “shape and the acetabular size that show differences when sex and age are considered”

DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION:

Discussion and conclusion are well written and clear but the discussion section is really too long and need to be summarized and shortened a lot, perhaps by focusing more on the application of the data learnt by this study to the field of anthropology and forensic sciences (as the estimation of age by analysing the acetabulum). Certainly, this study in my opinion is a descriptive study and this must be clearly addressed in the discussion. In fact, in the title talks about 'implications for adult age estimation', a point which needs to be discussed more critically.

At the beginning of the Discussion section we have highlighted that the study is descriptive “It is a descriptive study based on geometric morphometrics and associated statistical analysis.” In addition we have shortened the Discussion section and focused on the implications that this study has for adult age estimation based on the acetabulum. The most important conclusion is that when we estimate adult age based on the acetabulum we can use the same acetabular variables for males and females (they have the same ageing pattern). However, the reference samples for calculating estimated age using Bayes inference should be sex specific, because men and women have different acetabular ageing taxes. See the Discussion section.

Conclusion: I would suggest to the authors to rewrite the sentence 'With age, a relative masculinization of the acetabulum shape was observed in both sexes'. Perhaps they can just explain that in females the acetabular shape becomes more similar to the male ones with the ageing, and in the elderly the acetabular shape differences are far less noticeable between the two sexes.

We have rewritten this sentence.

GRAMMAR AND WORDING ADJUSTMENT:

Page 3, osteological material:

- **We analysed a total of 682 individuals (327 ♀, 355 ♂), originating from three modern documented skeletal collections' : change the term originating**

Page 4, second period:

- **Thus our sample has an age range of 15 to 101 years: change 'of' in 'from'**
- **Details regarding the age and sex of the sample, analysed by collection, are provided in Table 1: a wording adjustment is needed**

Page 5, landmarks and semilandmarks:

- **Following the protocol outlined in San Millán et al. (2015): change 'in' in 'by'**
-

Page 9 Section overall differences in acetabular size and shape:

- **In general, this section need to be rewritten in a correct wording (mentioned already in the material and methods' comments):**
- **'indicated that males and females differed significantly in acetabular size, while there were no significant differences in acetabular size among age groups' should be something like 'indicate that the acetabular size differs significantly in males and females but not among age group.'**

All of these suggested changes have been taken into account in the new version of the manuscript.

The English has also been reviewed thoroughly.

Reviewer #2

However, the discussion does not meet the expectations of the research, which is to describe why acetabular shape is important in age and sex estimation as well as hip surgeries. Rather, the discussion provides a repetition of the results section with an emphasis on the significant results of the finding and not the significance of the findings. The discussion needs to be reorganized to more clearly highlight the importance of the research. For example, "our results indicated a presence of significant shape differences between males and females younger than 65 years of age" is a repetition of what was presented in the results section. In the discussion, the author(s) need to more clearly explain and contextualize the value of the results of their research. While some of this was addressed in the discussion, it can, overall, be much better organized and made clearer for the reader. This will require a shortening of the text and a tightening up of the key points the authors want to get across.

Clarity can also be improved in the introduction. For example, the first sentence of the introduction can be removed, as the readers' of the journal will know the basic osteology of the acetabulum. Start the introduction with addressing why it is important to look at the acetabulum. Is this section of the os coxae important for sex and age estimation? Can it improve an estimation of sex from the pelvis? Or how about age estimation when combine with the pubic symphysis and the auricular surface?

The Introduction and Discussion section have been rewritten, improving both texts following your suggestions.

Small grammatical mistakes were noted.

On page 3, paragraph 1, the sentence "relatively recently", remove relatively.

On page 8, paragraph 1, " A PCA was performed for each sex", not each sexual sample.

Abstract, define what is meant by a native acetabulum.

The second paragraph on sex differences contains many "furthermore", "moreovers", "thus" and "in fact". Rewrite with a reduction in the number of conjunctions used to connect the various sentences.

The black arrows in Fig. 7B and C as well as Fig. 8 are a bit dark, white arrows may be easier to see.

All of these suggested changes have been taken into account in the new version of the manuscript.

The English has also been reviewed thoroughly.